

Emotion regulation intervention

A) Rumination intervention questionnaire (translated in english)

Instructions: Please focus your attention as fully as possible on each question on the following pages for the next few minutes. Take your time with each question, keeping in mind that you should spend a total time of exactly 15 minutes on this questionnaire.

Please read each question slowly and carefully. Write down all your thoughts and feelings about each question. Use the space provided below each question. You may provide your thoughts in full sentences or in bullet points. While reading each question, use your imagination and concentration, and try to tune into your inner experience to direct your attention to every aspect of the question.

Please continue until the experimenter returns.

1. If the situation you just experienced had been a real job interview, do you think you would have been selected by the panel for your dream job? If not, why not?

2. What did you do or say during the interview that you are now dissatisfied with?

3. How is your current mood, and what do you attribute it to?

4. In your opinion, did your mistakes or weaknesses during the interview lead the panel to form a negative impression of you? If yes, what opinion might the panel have of you now?

5. How tense were you in the situation you experienced, and how did you notice this? Why were you tense?

6. How well do you think you performed compared to the other study participants? What is the reason for this evaluation?

7. Did you experience a loss of control during the interview? If yes, how did this loss manifest, and how did you feel about it?

8. If you were stressed during the interview, did the stress affect your performance during the interview and the math task?

9. Did the panel notice that you were stressed? What impression might the panel have formed of you as a result?

10. If you faced the panel in a similar situation again, what would you fear?

B) Reappraisal intervention questionnaire (translated in english)

Instructions: Please focus your attention as fully as possible on each question on the following pages for the next few minutes. Take your time with each question, keeping in mind that you should spend a total time of exactly 15 minutes on the questionnaire.

Please read each question slowly and carefully. Write down all your thoughts and feelings about each question. Use the space provided below each question. You may provide your thoughts in full sentences or in bullet points. While reading each question, use your imagination and concentration, and try to tune into your inner experience to direct your attention to every aspect of the question.

Please continue until the experimenter returns.

1. Reflect on what you can take away from the interview for your future. What did you do well, and how could you leverage these strengths even more effectively next time?

2. If you were dissatisfied with yourself during the interview, try not to dwell on the past, as it cannot be changed. Instead, consider today's interview as a practice or training opportunity for future interviews. What did you learn today? How has the interview prepared you for similar situations in the future, and what positive outcomes might this have for you?

3. Try to view your performance from the perspective of a supportive friend. How would this person evaluate your performance? What would he/she say or advise you if you told her/him about the interview and the feelings it triggered?

4. Write down three positive aspects of today's interview and your performance. (*Did you experience any positive feelings during the interview? If so, which ones, and how could you enhance them? Did you experience any negative feelings during the interview? If so, which ones, and how could you transform them into positive feelings?*)

5. How did the panel come across to you? If you knew that the panel's reactions had nothing to do with you or your performance, what alternative explanation could you imagine?

6. In a stressful situation, the sympathetic nervous system is activated, leading to the release of adrenaline and noradrenaline. As a result, blood pressure and heart rate increase, sweating intensifies, breathing accelerates, and we become more alert, allowing us to respond more quickly to relevant stimuli in our environment. The brain receives more oxygen, and the senses are sharpened, so excitement can actually enhance our performance.

Which stress response did you notice in yourself today, and how could it have supported your performance?

7. Research has shown that even our attitude toward a stressor can influence how well we cope with it and whether we benefit from it.
What thought(s) could help you perceive the situation more as a challenge rather than a threat?

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- 8.** Imagine you were part of the panel and noticed stress symptoms (e.g., sweating, blushing) in a candidate. What positive explanations could you attribute to this reaction (e.g., motivation, ambition)?
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- 9.** Research has shown that stress does not inherently impair performance but can even enhance our ability to encode and retain information by increasing the activity of certain brain areas. Our cognitive functions can therefore benefit from stress. To what extent did you notice enhanced cognitive performance during the interview?
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- 10.** In an exciting situation, its effects often feel more severe than they actually are. Looking back on the interview, how significant was it for your future, and how does this perspective change your view of the situation and the feelings it triggered?
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C) Control questionnaire (translated in english)

Instructions: Please focus your attention as fully as possible on each question on the following pages for the next few minutes. Take your time with each question, keeping in mind that you should spend a total time of exactly 15 minutes on the questionnaire.

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Please continue until the experimenter returns.

1. Why is the job you selected in the interview your dream job?
2. Which job would be absolutely unsuitable for you, and why?
3. What was your dream job as a child, and why?
4. In your opinion, which characteristics best qualify a boss?
5. In your opinion, what qualities make a good colleague?
6. Where do you see yourself professionally in 10 years?
7. In your view, what factors make a workplace attractive?
8. What does work-life balance mean to you? How important is work-life balance for you, and how do you implement it in your daily life?
9. An assessment center (AC) is a method used to evaluate individuals in the context of personnel selection and development to assess candidates' competencies. What is your general opinion on the use of ACs? On what criteria would you base your selection of candidates?
10. What is your opinion on the topic of "introducing a quota for women in leadership positions"?